

SUGGESTIONS AIMED AT THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This thesis includes suggestions to eliminate existing deficiencies in the preschool education system in Uzbekistan. The suggestions are the result of a detailed study of existing shortcomings.

Introduction: Preschool Child Development and Education (PCDE) is an integral part of the joint programs between UNICEF and the Government in the areas of education, health, child protection and communication. Access to PCDE services, including preschool services, helps children develop and prepare for school in the early years of their lives. Preparing young children for school is one of UNICEF's priorities in the field of education.

Main part: In order to improve the quality of public preschools, the government should pass a resolution that states instructors who have an English Language certificate (CEFR, IELTS) would get a higher wage. Money is, in fact, the most effective form of motivation. During my research, I have interviewed several preschool instructors, and all of them have said that, without any concerns, they are ready to take this sort of certificate program, provided that the government

pays an additional fee for it. Studies indicate that increasing the quality of the teaching staff is crucial; however, it is also essential to provide students with an appropriate curriculum that is delivered at the appropriate pace and in a language of instruction that is acceptable. The requirement of covering an overly ambitious curriculum is often the major reason that acts as the basis for establishing the speed at which classroom instruction is delivered, rather than the rate at which pupils are really absorbing the subject matter. Too many of the world's educational systems were designed by and for the ruling classes of the countries in which they were implemented. Because of this, the curriculum taught in schools typically reflects the culture or language that is most prevalent in the nation, or at the absolute least, these subjects have relatively little bearing on the students' everyday life.

Since money is the primary factor that motivates instructors, the government needs to organize competitions for which participants would get extra compensation. For instance, those who come out on top in competitions for titles like "best trainer," "best manager," and "best defector" will get bonuses ranging from 5 to 15 times the minimum pay.

In addition to that, there is a draught resolution concerning the education of children aged 6 years old. Educators who deal with children less than 6 years old should be considered for promotion to the teaching ranks. Therefore, it is to be assumed that the advantages that are presently being put into place in the Ministry of Public Education would, at some point in the future, apply to them as well.

Those individuals who make a request for more services will also have access to additional services that need payment. Uzbekistan's Resolution No. 414 asks for the growth of extra-budgetary activities as well as the state itself, thus it is important to keep this in mind. The pedagogical staff of the preschools are the ones who determine how the money should be spent since pre-schooling is an independent activity that goes within their control.

A further key objective that we need to consider is providing all children with access to a preschool education system that is of an equally high standard and justification. There are certain rural regions in Uzbekistan that do not have any kindergartens, which means that there is no access to pre-school education in such places. In fact, a considerable proportion of children are unable to acquire even the most fundamental of knowledge. Statistics (yuz.uz) indicate that there are 18,254 preschool groups that are responsible for

the upbringing of 1,699,566 preschool children, which indicates that around 40 percent of kids do not attend school. The results of this analysis are quite disastrous. The international community has committed, under Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4, to ensuring that all children have access to equitable and high-quality primary and secondary education by the year 2030. The job at hand now is to make these assertions a reality by tackling the various difficulties of quality and inequality that exist in countries with education systems that are lacking in strength. In order to find a solution to this issue, the government needs to make resources, both financial and physical, available to family organizations so that they may establish one-room preschools. It is possible that this solution may seem to be unimportant; but, if the government is successful in carrying out this initiative, a sizeable number of youngsters will have the opportunity to acquire information that is invaluable.

Indeed, all the solutions that have been given above are being responsible by the government, while teachers should be extremely hard working and attentive. The extent to which education expenditure by governments may have an impact on economic inequality is highly dependent not just on how much money is spent where, on what kind of education, and who benefits from it, but also on the kind of education itself. Taxing those who are wealthiest and most able to pay for universal free education has a significant impact on promoting equality and battling poverty for the benefit of the nation. This is because universal free education benefits everyone. At least one hundred billion dollars are lost by developing countries each year because of tax avoidance by corporations; this

amount is equivalent to half of what is believed to be required to cover the annual cost of providing universal access to elementary and lower secondary education in low-income countries.

Spending money on public services and social security has been identified by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) as one of the most effective strategies for reducing poverty and addressing inequality. More than 150 countries, rich and poor alike, saw a reduction in inequality because of investments made in education and other public services during a period of 30 years. 324 Research after study has proven that public spending has had a levelling effect on all the low- and middle-income countries that were included in the study. Education played a significant part in both the alleviation of poverty and the advancement of social equality in these countries.

As Anderson Potocnik claimed that creativity and innovation can occur at the level of the individual, work team, organization, or at more than one of these levels, I have reached these solutions both individually and collaborating with colleagues as well. In the beginning, it was exceedingly difficult for me to find a proper solution to this problem. As Helmholtz described how "happy ideas came unexpectedly without effort, like an inspiration", these solutions had come daily of mine. Besides, I also agree with the statement of Steve Johnson, who makes the crucial point that creative ideas come out of inter-connectivity and social exchanges.

According to the findings of this study, the only way we will be able to do this is if we alter the public education system such that it prioritizes both quality and equality. Implementing the policies that are stated in this report is the only way to achieve this

goal. A focus in education that focuses primarily on privatization, competition, and the illusion of 'choice' will result in an increase in inequality. A path fraught with peril, particularly for the youth of today who are presented with a world that is undergoing rapid transformation. It will not meet the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) goal of providing an equal and high-quality education for everyone by 2030, which would require a notable change in the policies and expenditures in most developing nations to achieve. Even though the economic inequality between wealthy and poor continues to grow, it results in a dramatic growth in income and wealth inequality, the gap between the rich and the poor, as well as males and women, is expanding. Because of this, we will not be able to achieve our objective, which is to reduce poverty and inequality. The fact that women strive to compensate a disproportionate part of the world's poor only helps to reinforce gender inequality and hinders the achievement of women's rights. This is because women try to compensate a disproportionate number of the world's poor. These imbalances pose a risk to the social contract that exists between the state and its citizens because they undermine social cohesion and the democratic institutions that maintain it.

On the other hand, inequality is not an unavoidable fact. From a political standpoint, a choice must be made. Both national governments and international organizations have deliberated and decided upon this course of action. It is frequently and universally believed that extreme inequality may be prevented, and that meaningful efforts can be taken to minimize inequality. In other words, there is a possibility that inequality can be reduced.

Conclusion: Through the medium of education of the highest caliber, both individuals and society have the potential to be emancipated. This research has shown that education has the potential to level the playing field, to assist in bridging the

growing divides, and to bring us closer together. "When there are millions of children who are refused an education that gives them respect and honour and enables them to fully live their life, no one can be pleased."

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